

**THE ESSENCE OF THE LEGACY OF ABU NASR FARABI, HIS
TEACHING ON SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION.**

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Abstract: The article contains philosophy, logic, education and training. The essence of the legacy of the famous scientist Abu Nasr Farabi. Based on available sources, the didactic value of the high spiritual and moral ideas put forward in it is analytically analyzed. Their use in the modern pedagogical process is interpreted as an important social necessity.

Key words: knowledge, education, educational process, spiritual and moral ideas, human qualities, content of education, teaching methods, methodological support.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the social and spiritual life of society, ensuring the spiritual growth of the individual is considered as a set of eternal goals and noble aspirations of humanity. The core work of leaders in science, education and development is distinguished by its focus on these issues. In particular, the main goal of the scientific, creative and practical activity of the great thinkers of the East throughout their lives, regardless of the area and direction, was to increase the

spiritual and spiritual maturity of a person, thereby strengthening the health of all people. humanity. society. , develop it and reach new heights of development. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev: “We are all part of the education and training system. We consider our main priority to be the improvement of its activities, based on the requirements of today”, as well as “The desire of the people for a certain goal” by Fitrat, to be a statesman, to be happy and respected, to be worldly or weak and despised”, to bear the burden of adversity, to be neglected, to obey others, to be a slave, a captive - this is their childhood, it depends on the education that he received from his parents¹,” said the head of our state.

This is proof of how responsible we are for the welfare of the people, the future of children, their education. After all, children are our future, they are the successors of the work of our parents and ancestors. As the President noted: “Undoubtedly, the upbringing of culture, intellectual and spiritual potential, which is the greatest wealth of our national history and the world, with deep respect, enriching it and, on this basis, educating the younger generation in the spirit of national and universal values is of decisive importance.” role in the material and spiritual development of every state and society in the world.”

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Encyclopedic scholars used their talents and capabilities to achieve these goals. We see this widely in the works of such great scientists as Ibn Sina, Beruni, Khorezmi, Farabi, Rumi, Rudaki Fargani. Therefore, it is impossible to scientifically solve the issues of educating young people as perfect people in all respects, without knowing how the practice of educating the younger generation developed. This is a scientific, theoretical, philosophical and educational fact proven by our ancestors. In-depth study of historical traditions, spiritual wealth, scientific heritage and historical and educational experience of our ancestors, implementation of their achievements, education of spiritually pure and mature

people in educational work. It is very important to successfully solve the task. Raising a perfect generation is a social phenomenon, an ancient and eternal value that ensures the formation of personality as the main criterion that determines the existence of the individual and society passing from generation to generation. In particular, the rich scientific, philosophical, spiritual and educational heritage of Abu Nasr Farabi, world-famous as the “Second Teacher” after Aristotle, is of particular importance in this regard. The use of Alloma's teachings on spiritual and moral education in the educational process of the general secondary and higher education system is extremely effective today. The main direction of Abu Nasr Farabi's research covers the study of human structure, the psyche, the material and spiritual world. As a mature philosopher, Farabi tries to study and interpret mental processes depending on the mental, moral and spiritual maturity of a person. That is why in his works he pays great attention to such processes as intuition, mental cognition, and also talks about other mental processes such as memory, imagination, attention, emotions, will, abilities, skills, etc. It is known that development thinking and speech, characteristic of a person and important for his spiritual growth, is an important process that forms the basis of education. Pharaoh deeply studies the qualities of human thinking and speech, develops the science of grammar and logic, analyzes some of its issues and pays great attention to it. The idea is put forward that the spiritual growth of a person should be the main and main goal in educational processes based on acquired knowledge. To Farabi interpretation, in his opinion, man is the most perfect and mature completion of world development. That is why, in his scientific and practical work, he focused on the need for education and training and what should be the basis of this, methods of education and training, as well. like targets eluding him. In particular, his works such as “The City of the Virtuous”, “On Finding Happiness”, “Ikhsa al-Ulum”, “On the Meaning of Reason” have high spiritual and moral qualities. Such problems are carefully analyzed and important recommendations are put forward.

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Educational process, according to Farabi, an experienced educator is a teacher. must be organized, managed and directed towards specific goals, since “everyone wants happiness and events that he cannot know for himself. For this he needs a teacher.” The development of pharaonic thinking and speech is an important process characteristic of a person, it is important for his spiritual growth and forms the basis of education. The scientist believes that “hard” or “soft” methods should be used in the educational process, depending on the nature of the children: “if students are inclined to study and learn, a soft method is used in the educational process; If students are disobedient and disobedient, a strict method should be used.” Alloma's moral and educational ideas are aimed, first of all, at knowing the great creator - Allah, at mastering the science and knowledge created by humanity, and laid the foundation for important tools and methods of the educational process. In the spiritual life of the pharaoh, much attention is paid to two sides of a person: his mind and morality (behavior). Therefore, according to scientists, education is the intellectual side of a person, which should be oriented towards in order to make him a mature and perfect person, both intellectually and morally. Therefore, the only task of education is to prepare an ideal person who can fully satisfy the needs of society and serve to preserve its unity, peace and prosperity. The opinion of Abu Nasr Farabi: “It is not enough for a person to see and feel beauty in order to achieve his happiness; for this it is important to be able to create beauty” has universal significance. According to this thinker, our parents are responsible for their family, work, daily life, household chores, relationships, behavior, clothing, health, raising and treating children. He has the idea that he should be able to create beauty. expressed himself. Our ancestors set an example and gave advice to their children. For example, Abu Nasr Farabi said: “Every person should know his profession perfectly, receive a good education, have good manners and virtues.” In society, everyone loves polite, educated, intelligent, proactive, active people. The purpose of presenting the thoughts of our thinkers on education, science and

science is that we hope that they will serve to effectively utilize the education of children. Farobi wrote such works as “Opinions of the Residents of Fazil”, “Treatise on Achieving Happiness” and “Ways to Achieving Happiness”, dedicated to socio-political issues. Farobi emphasizes that in a virtuous city the importance of science, philosophy, morals and education must come first, and only then will the society mature. In his opinion, the ability of man and society to win, to achieve good, to achieve moral and intellectual perfection is in the hands of man and society, and knowledge and enlightenment must be decorated with excellent morality. We not only need knowledge, but education is also necessary. No wonder our wise people said: “A child’s manners are beautiful.”

CONCLUSION

A person has good habits and actions only when he has knowledge and good morals. can embody, does not bring any nasty dirty tricks into the street, on the contrary, he stubbornly fights them. The advanced ideas of philosophy, logic, anthropology and social sciences put forward by this great spiritual and moral educator and scientist-teacher are a positive education for the development of future scientists and teachers' views on education and human development. The thinker’s teaching about ethics and the education of the younger generation on its basis have not lost their importance, but now, on the contrary, they are acquiring great importance in the development and development of new methods and rules of moral education. It becomes an important resource for the correct and systematic implementation of the processes of spiritual and moral education, improving scientific and methodological support.

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